

Effect of Surfactants on Oxalic Acid catalysed Oxidation of Aromatic Azo Compounds by Chromium(VI)

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Effect of surfactants of different charge type on the rate of oxalic acid catalysed oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl benzene azodimethylaniline (BADMA) by Cr^{VI} in 10% acetic acid medium has been investigated. Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) inhibited while polyoxyethylene(23) dodecanol (Brij-35) catalysed the reactions. 10⁻² M SDS and CTAB inhibited the oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl BADMA. Catalytic effect of 10⁻² M Brij 35 has been investigated. These effects are discussed on the basis of interactions of the above aromatic azo compounds with the micelles of different charge type. Binding parameters have been calculated by analysing the data using a model suggested by Piskiewicz. Influence of surfactants on the activation parameters of the reactions has been discussed.

Several studies have been undertaken to understand the interactions responsible for rate enhancement and retardation in micelle forming surfactants¹. But there are no reports on the micellar effects on the rate of oxidation of aromatic azo compounds by metal ions. Kinetic studies on the oxidation of some aromatic azo compounds by Cr^{VI} catalysed by oxalic acid in aqueous acetic acid medium have been reported². We present here the catalytic effect of micelle forming surfactants, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS) and polyoxyethylene (23) dodecanol (Brij-35) on the oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl benzene azodimethylaniline (BADMA) by Cr^{VI} in 10% acetic acid medium. This study attempts at understanding the nature of interactions responsible for catalytic and inhibitory effects of micelles on the rate of oxidation of the aromatic azo compounds.

Results and Discussion

Effect of cationic surfactant CTAB, anionic surfactant SDS and nonionic surfactant Brij-35 on the rate of oxalic acid catalysed oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl benzene azodimethylaniline by Cr^{VI} in 10% acetic acid medium has been investigated. Surfactant effects were studied by keeping the concentration of chromic acid very high compared to that of the azo compounds. The plots of log (absorbance) versus time were found to be linear indicating that the reaction is first order with respect to each of the azo compounds in micellar medium.

Comparison of rate constants (Table 1) in 10⁻² M concentrations of surfactants shows that (i) SDS inhibits the oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl BADMA by 1.4, 7, 5 and 9 times respectively, (ii) CTAB inhibits the oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl BADMA by 2.4, 7, 4 and 1.5 times respectively and (iii) Brij-35 catalytic effect on the oxidation of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH *p*-COOH

TABLE 1—RATE CONSTANTS FOR OXIDATION OF *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl BADMA BY Cr^{VI} IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS

[Azo compound]=2×10⁻⁶ M, [Cr^{VI}]=2×10⁻⁴ M, [(COOH)₂]=1×10⁻² M, [H⁺]=0.1 M, μ=0.11, [Surfactant]=1×10⁻² M, temp.=298 K, medium: 10% acetic acid-water

Surfactant	10 ⁴ k (s ⁻¹)			
	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	<i>o</i> -COOH	<i>p</i> -COOH	<i>p</i> -Cl
No surfactant	10.94	8.08	35.43	20.66
Brij-35	12.51	12.33	60.31	167.90
SDS	7.81	1.08	6.85	21.32
CTAB	4.45	1.19	7.90	13.86

BADMA is little but on that of *p*-Cl BADMA is 8 times. Fig. 1 shows the effect of varying SDS concentration on the rate of oxidation of *o*-COOH *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl BADMA. Variation of rate constant for the oxidation of *p*-Cl BADMA with increasing concentrations of Brij-35 is shown in Fig. 2.

Effects of varying Cr^{VI}, H⁺, oxalic acid and azo compound concentrations on the rate of oxidation in presence and absence of surfactants have been found to be similar. This indicates that the mechanism of oxidation is the same in both the media. A mechanism similar to that reported earlier for the oxidation of the azo compounds is in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

This mechanism leads to the rate equation,

$$-\frac{d[\text{Azo compound}]}{dt} = k' K K' [\text{HCrO}_4^-] [(\text{COOH})_2] [\text{Azo compound}] [\text{H}^+]$$

Fig. 1. Effect of SDS concentration on the rate of oxidation of (□) *o*-COOH BADMA, (○) *p*-COOH BADMA and (△) *p*-Cl BADMA by Cr^{VI}; [Azo compound]=2×10⁻⁵ M, [Cr^{VI}]=2×10⁻⁴ M, [(COOH)₂]=1×10⁻³ M, [H⁺]=0.1 M, μ=0.11, temp.=298 K solvent=10% aqueous acetic acid.

Fig. 2. Effect of Brij-35 concentration on the rate of oxidation of *p*-Cl BADMA by Cr^{VI}; [Azo compound]=2×10⁻⁵ M, [Cr^{VI}]=2×10⁻⁴ M, [(COOH)₂]=1×10⁻³ M, [H⁺]=0.1 M, μ=0.11, temp.=298 K, solvent=10% aqueous acetic acid.

Catalytic and inhibitory effects of micelles can be interpreted on the basis of the mechanism and the possible interactions between the reacting species and micelles of different charge type. In 0.1 *M* hydrogen ion concentration where the reactions were carried out, the azo compounds predominantly exist as neutral species. These neutral azo compounds bind to cationic micelles of CTAB or anionic micelles of SDS due to hydrophobic interactions. Partitioning of H^+ between SDS micelles and aqueous bulk phase will shift the protonation equilibrium to the left (Scheme 1). Distribution of $HCrO_4^-$ and X^- between CTAB micelles and bulk phase will also have the same effect. This decreases the concentration of the oxidising species XH. XH is neither associated with enough hydrophobic character nor hydrophilic character to interact with the micelles. So, the fraction of azo compound to micelles may not be readily available for the attack by XH. Thus inhibition in CTAB and SDS may be attributed to the decrease in XH concentration and lower rate of attack of XH towards micelle bound substrate compared to that in the bulk phase.

In contrast to inhibition of oxidation in ionic micelles of CTAB or SDS, catalysis in nonionic micelles of Brij-35 may be due to relatively strong binding of azo compounds to Brij-35 micelles as a result of favourable hydrophobic interactions. Unlike in the presence of ionic micelles, no electrostatic forces are operative in Brij-35 micelles to affect XH distribution in micellar and aqueous phases. Enhanced concentration of substrate in micellar phase must be responsible for increased rate of reaction in this phase resulting in the observed catalysis.

The data of variation of the observed rate constant k_ψ , with concentration of SDS, for *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl BADMA and with concentration of Brij-35 for *p*-Cl BADMA are analysed on the basis of the model proposed by Piszkiwicz⁸ (Scheme 2).

TABLE 2—PARAMETERS DERIVED FROM HILL-TYPE PLOTS FOR OXIDATION OF *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl BADMA IN SDS AND *p*-Cl BADMA IN BRIJ-35 BY Cr^{VI}

Substrate and Surfactant	<i>n</i>	$\log [D]_{50} \cdot 10^3$	$1/K_D$	Corr. coeff.
<i>o</i> -COOH BADMA in SDS	1.31	-3.05	9.9	0.987 5
<i>p</i> -COOH BADMA in SDS	1.63	-2.75	30.3	0.995 5
<i>p</i> -Cl BADMA in SDS	0.83	-3.9	1.7	0.994 5
<i>p</i> -Cl BADMA in Brij-35	0.86	-2.34	0.1	0.981 5

Scheme 2

Here substrate S, and a number *n* of detergent molecules of D, aggregate to form catalytic micelles, D_nS , which may then react to yield products. K_D is the dissociation constant of the micelle back to

its free components. k_m and k_o are the rate constants in micellar and aqueous phases respectively. Scheme 2 gives the following expression for the observed rate constant,

$$k_\psi = \frac{k_m[D]^n + k_o K_D}{K_D + [D]^n} \quad (1)$$

Rearrangement of this equation gives

$$\log \frac{(k_\psi - k_o)}{(k_m - k_\psi)} = n \log [D] - \log K_D \quad (2)$$

In analysing the data according to Scheme 2, k_m is taken as the maximum reaction value of observed rate constant for catalysed reaction and lowest value of observed rate constant for inhibited reactions. As required by equation (2), plots of $\log (k_\psi - k_o)/(k_m - k_\psi)$ vs $\log [D]$ for Brij-35 catalysed oxidation of *p*-Cl BADMA and for SDS inhibited oxidation of *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl BADMA have been found to be linear (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Analysis of the effect of SDS on the oxidation of (○) *o*-COOH BADMA, (□) *p*-COOH BADMA, (△) *p*-Cl BADMA and the effect of Brij-35 on the oxidation of (●) *p*-Cl BADMA by Cr^{VI} .

High correlation coefficient values (Table 2) obtained for the plots indicate that the data fits well in to the model and justifies simplified representation of multiple aggregation steps into two steps as shown in Scheme 2. Values of *n*, $\log [D]_{50}$ and $1/K_D$ obtained from the plots are given in Table 2. $\log [D]_{50}$ values represent the concentration of detergent required for half-maximal catalysis or inhibition of reaction. They are found to be lower than the known critical micelle concentrations⁴. This demonstrates the existence of functional submicellar aggregates involving detergent and substrate molecules of varying stoichiometries. The values of

TABLE 3—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl BADMA BY Cr^{VI} IN ABSENCE AND PRESENCE OF SURFACTANTS

[Azo compound]= 2×10^{-3} M, [Cr^{VI}]= 2×10^{-4} M, [H⁺]=0.1 M, [(COOH)₂]= 1×10^{-3} M, μ =0.11, [Surfactant]= 1×10^{-3} M, medium: 10% acetic acid-water

Parameter	<i>o</i> -COOH BADMA				<i>p</i> -COOH BADMA				<i>p</i> -Cl BADMA			
	No surfactant	Brij-35	SDS	CTAB	No surfactant	Brij-35	SDS	CTAB	No surfactant	Brij-35	SDS	CTAB
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	42.1	38.5	42.3	45.7	40.7	37.4	8.4	55.9	51.1	60.9	16.9	31.7
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	90.2	88.7	95.2	94.7	94.1	91.5	96.7	93.8	94.8	89.0	95.2	94.1
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-133	-168	-178	-164	-179	-182	-309	-127	-146	-125	-245	-209

$n > 1$ are viewed as indication of the substrate induced micellisation. Observed effect of detergents at pre-micellar concentrations can be attributed to this. Considering the degree of uncertainty in the evaluation of n values, as pointed out by Piskiewicz, no conclusion has been drawn on the basis of n values observed for the oxidation of *p*-Cl BADMA in SDS and Brij-35. Values of $1/K_D$ (Table 2) indicate the existence of significant detergent-substrate interactions in all the four cases analysed. This suggests that it is more appropriate to view n as representing average stoichiometry of the detergent-substrate aggregate.

The differences in the oxidation rates of *p*-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH and *p*-Cl BADMA in micellar media indicate that the interactions between the azo compounds and micelles are specific in nature and are dependent on the nature of the substituents.

Temperature effect in absence and presence of surfactants: Arrhenius plots for the oxidation of *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl BADMA in absence and presence of 0.01 M SDS, Brij-35 and CTAB have been found to be linear (figure not shown). Activation parameters E_a , ΔS^\ddagger and ΔG^\ddagger , calculated from the plots are listed in Table 3. Very little catalytic effect of Brij-35 on the rate of oxidation of *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH BADMA can be understood in terms of decrease in activation energy. Eight-fold catalysis of the oxidation of *p*-Cl BADMA by Brij-35 may be due to favourable entropy of activation. Inhibitory effect of SDS by about 7 times on the oxidation of *o*-COOH can be attributed to unfavourable entropy of activation. 5 and 9 times inhibition of the oxidation of *p*-COOH BADMA and *p*-Cl BADMA by SDS may be due to relatively large negative value of ΔS^\ddagger in anionic micelles of SDS. Inhibition of about 7 times by CTAB on the oxidation of *o*-COOH BADMA may be due to the combined contribution of increase in activation energy and unfavourable entropy of activation (Table 3). Inhibitory effect of CTAB by about 4 times on the oxidation of *p*-COOH BADMA may be ascribed to 15.2 kJ mol⁻¹ increase in activation energy. Small inhibitory effect of CTAB on the oxidation of *p*-Cl BADMA is

due to opposing contributions of E_a and ΔS^\ddagger . Nearly equal ΔG^\ddagger values for the reactions in absence and presence of micelles confirms that the reaction mechanism is same in both the media.

Experimental

p-SO₃H, *o*-COOH, *p*-COOH, *p*-Cl benzene azo-dimethylanilines were prepared by reported methods⁶. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and sodium dodecyl sulphate were purified by recrystallisation⁶. Brij-35 (Koch-light) was used. All other chemicals used were of analytical grade.

Kinetic measurements were carried out spectrophotometrically using a Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer by observing decrease in absorbance of *p*-SO₃H BADMA at 507.5 nm, of *o*-COOH BADMA at 522 nm, of *p*-COOH BADMA at 508.5 nm and of *p*-Cl BADMA at 515 nm as a function of time. Other species have negligible absorption at these wavelengths. Ionic strength was maintained constant using potassium chloride. The cell containing reaction mixture was maintained at the desired temperature with a precision of $\pm 0.1^\circ$ by using a cryostatic bath which circulated water around the cell holder jacket of the spectrophotometer. Calculations and analysis of the kinetic data was carried out using a DCM personal computer.

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